

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Managing ethical education activities for university students in the current period

Tran Khai Minh Phap *

Faculty of Information technology, FPT University, Vietnam.

GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 13(03), 109–112

Publication history: Received on 01 November 2022; revised on 07 December 2022; accepted on 10 December 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2022.13.3.0360>

Abstract

In the process of national renewal, the market mechanism and the multi-sector commodity economy are promoting positive effects, at the same time revealing the downside, negatively affecting cultural and spiritual life. as well as the psychology and morality of all classes of people in society, including the youth, especially the current student class at small and large universities across the country. In the current period of industrialization and modernization, along with the positive changes in the country, we are also facing the challenges of the times, that is, a part of young people has the phenomenon of depression, moral degradation, fading of ideals and pursuing a pragmatic lifestyle. Many social evils are creeping into the school, making a part of student's degenerate, slow to progress, difficult to educate, even corrupt, and violate the law. The problem is how to both develop the economy and society while maintaining and promoting the noble and beautiful human values in each person. Properly assess the situation, properly identify the problem, detect obstacles and obstacles, find the causes and propose measures to well manage the moral education for students at major universities. small and small children in the country is an urgent job today to contribute to ensuring the quality of education of the school, meeting the requirements of human resource training for the country.

Keywords: Ethics; Innovation; Development; Education; Students

1. Introduction

People have a passionate patriotism; it is a precious tradition of the nation. From the past to the present, every time the Vietnam country was invaded, that spirit was vibrant, it formed an extremely powerful and huge wave, it surmounted all dangers and difficulties. It is a complete and comprehensive generalization for the will and strength of Vietnamese people who never tremble in the face of difficulties, challenges, and dangers, even when faced between life and death, the spirit of immortal The death for the Fatherland is still burning in each specific person, and President Ho Chi Minh is the most representative of the mettle [1].

It is rare for any nation in the world to have as many good traditional moral values as ours, the history of fighting against foreign invaders, and the requirements of wet-rice agriculture that have been tempered, formed, and developed. develop many good qualities of the nation, that as patriotism, resilient and indomitable fighting spirit, not being afraid of difficulties and dangers, being ready to rush into the place of "arrows and bullets"; hardworking, intelligence, creativity, loyal, comrade-in-arms, helping each other in all conditions and circumstances; village love, neighborliness, fire, and light together, selling brothers far away to buy neighbors near, etc. These qualities are the crystallization of traditional morality that is forged through the practice of movement, development, and transformation of society and is increasingly proven in practice, by the enduring and sustainable vitality of traditional morality that never fades, becomes forgotten, becomes the belief, and reason of life determines the direction of awareness and action of the people each for the goal of a rich people, a strong country, democracy, justice, and civilization [2].

* Corresponding author: Tran Khai Minh Phap
Faculty of Information technology, FPT University, Vietnam.

2. Ethics concept

Ethics is a very broad category that is expressed in all aspects of social life, but in the most common sense, morality is expressed as the spirit and action for others, for the people and society; spirit of serving the people, serving others. In a broad sense: morality is a form of social consciousness used to adjust human behavior to suit the interests of happiness and enrich humanity in social relations. In the narrow sense: ethics are morals, standards, and codes of conduct in the relationship between people and people, work, themselves, nature, and the living environment [3].

Thus, Ho Chi Minh's thought on morality is the rules, standards, and principles of moral training and cultivation set forth by Ho Chi Minh that are recognized by society and used as a principle to regulate relations between people and children. people during the process of building and perfecting a new human being - a socialist man [4].

3. Comparing knowledge and ethics education for students

Each subject has its position and role in the teaching process and makes an important contribution to providing knowledge, training skills, and forming students' professional attitudes. Moral education for students does not simply stop at any particular subject but is a resonance of all subjects. Some lecturers only focus on completing the amount of knowledge in their lecture content for students and students, but pay little attention to moral education for students because of time constraints when going to class. Moreover, the results of moral education for students are not shown immediately after each lesson, but rather the results of the entire educational process with a combination of many subjects [5].

The field of moral education for students must be comprehensively realized through learning attitudes, behaviors, spirits, attitudes at work, and responsibility in performing tasks as learners. Therefore, in each subject, teachers must be responsible for directing students and students to properly perceive and behave appropriately in each specific situation [3].

Ethical education for students through behavior and problem solving of lecturers. In any class, there may be normal communication situations in or out of the teacher's expectations. Therefore, students can learn how to handle situations from teachers to be more flexible and skillful when meeting specific situations. At the same time, the expressions of handling situations in communication also give a good impression to the children [6].

4. The need for ethics education for students

Students are a class of people who play a very important role in the development of society. To promote the role of students, it is necessary to pay attention to thoroughly educating students. Which, moral education in general and moral education, in particular, are fundamental and fundamental tasks. Therefore, moral education for students is very necessary [3].

As the rules, standards, and value ladders to regulate human behavior, morality plays a very important role in every society, in the history of human development [4]. An important role in every society. In the history of human development, society has never been absent or lacking in the presence of morality. Ethics is one of the basic methods to regulate the behavior of individuals, the whole community, and the relationships between people and people in society, contributing to maintaining socio-political stability. which promotes the development of society, contributing to making people live humanely and humanely. Therefore, the more advanced the society, the more science, and technology development, and the more morality is needed. Therefore, students need to practice ethics to become good citizens, worthy of being the future owner of a country [5].

The second is derived from the position and role of youth and students in the development of the country. Students are a very important part of society, hold a leading position, and are one of the factors that determine the future and destiny of the nation. Students are the age of physical and intellectual enrichment, are always action, creative, explore new things, are a contributing force in many areas of social life, and undertake jobs that require enthusiasm, health, sacrifice, hardship.

5. The reality of ethics education for students in Vietnam

Students are a young force, a reserve force for future intellectuals, but they are also immature, inexperienced, easily manipulated, seduced, and agitated. Society is increasingly developing, and the opportunities for exchange and

cooperation are increasingly expanded, especially in the market economy and international integration in our country today, the introduction of cultural and ethical values from the outside will be stronger, and faster [8]. The negative impact of external factors has caused a large number of students to show signs of degradation in morality and lifestyle such as fading beliefs, ideals, and disorientation to strive; In learning, there is also the phenomenon of plagiarism, running score, running by, indifferent to mass activities, because of fear of difficulties and suffering, should be pragmatic in choosing a career; Some lifestyles follow the money, enjoy, compete, play, indulge, leading to breaking the law, violating moral standards and falling into social evils, etc. In terms of morality, this lifestyle not only endangers the current social life but also adversely affects the future of the country and the students themselves [7]. That shows that moral education in the university environment has not yet achieved the best effect. Universities tend to be more focused on specialization than on moral education, and some people think that ethics can be acquired by social frictions. The current university environment tends to let students loose, not to mention the moral education that only focuses on whether professional efficiency is good or not.

6. Some implications

Promote propaganda and education to raise awareness and responsibility for students about the role of traditional moral education. This is an important measure of leading significance to improve the quality of moral education for students at universities today [7]. Subjects in charge of management, education, and training, such as lecturers, student management offices, examination rooms, Youth Unions, and Student Associations at all levels, regularly propagate and educate students to understand and ensure the viewpoints, lines, undertakings, cities, and laws of the Party and State on youth and youth work in the period of accelerating industrialization and modernization of the country; directives and regulations of the Party on building and developing Vietnamese culture and people in the new period; The goal of the campaign to build a role model of youth with a clear heart, bright mind and great ambition by the Central Committee of the Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union, etc. The Youth Union and Student Unions at all levels need to be concretized and institutionalized in for each operation of the unit, to develop appropriate and effective emulation criteria and content for students to strive and grow to achieve the set goals and aspirations; propagating and educating the good traditional qualities of Vietnamese people, especially the State laws and regulations of the school; educating and fostering motivations, attitudes and responsibilities for students for the central political task of studying and training to become "both pink" and "professional" people of society; educating and fostering a clean and healthy cultural lifestyle, living honestly, altruistically, and being responsible for self, collective and society; stay away from a lavish, depraved, anti-cultural and unethical lifestyle that is inconsistent with the nation's fine customs and traditions and the school's rules; well promote the roles and responsibilities of the subjects in action coordination [9].

Regularly renewing content, forms, and methods of training mobile phones for university students. Fostering needs to apply flexibly, and creatively, not to be forced, mechanical, or passive in the subjects of leading, managing, and fostering students. Through examination results at the end of the course or subject to assess the quality of students' fostering activities; through practical activities at the unit, participating enthusiastically and responsibly in the union movements, organized by the Student Union; through emulation, commendation, honoring and praising the example of good people and good deeds, replicating advanced examples for students who have achieved high achievements in learning, training, participating in movement activities, scientific research; to build and set up student groups and groups to do propaganda, mobilize and help students and people in the locality.

7. Conclusion

Students are both the object of fostering and the subject of self-improvement, needing to wake up and arouse their dynamism and creativity at all times and places. No one can replace or do it for students with their efforts, trying to rise at all times and places of students for self-improvement to improve their capacity, qualifications, moral qualities, and ways of living. It is overcoming temptation, conquering yourself in the best way, not being satisfied with the results you already have, but always being humble, learning, and progressing according to the motto, if you don't know, learn, if you are weak, improve. care there. Accordingly, the positivity and initiative of students must be expressed in high spirit and responsibility towards themselves, their families, and society; in developing a plan for self-improvement and training with assigned jobs and tasks; in listening, and observing people around; must regularly cultivate thrown morality and lifestyle, especially in cultural relations with the social and natural environment; put yourself inside the organization, not stand above the organization or stand outside the organization; must take advantage of every hour, every minute to study, practice, supplement experience, life capital, understanding for themselves in various fields of social life; at the same time, proactively seize opportunities and opportunities, create favorable conditions, and prepare in all aspects to carry out the set plans. Every student in the future, no matter where he goes, does anything, no matter what position,

has to rise on his own, can't rely on the help of others, and consider it just for reference and orientation, the decision remains with each student himself, in the maturity and independence of their thoughts and actions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to send warm thanks to those who have supported to complete the paper as well as great advice for this research.

References

- [1] Colby, A., & Sullivan, W. M. (2008). Ethics teaching in undergraduate engineering education. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 97(3), 327-338.
- [2] Monteverde, S. (2014). Undergraduate healthcare ethics education, moral resilience, and the role of ethical theories. *Nursing ethics*, 21(4), 385-401.
- [3] Doan, D. H. (2005). Moral education or political education in the Vietnamese educational system?. *Journal of Moral Education*, 34(4), 451-463.
- [4] Mayhew, B. W., & Murphy, P. R. (2009). The impact of ethics education on reporting behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 86(3), 397-416.
- [5] Dzurani, A. C., Shortridge, R. T., & Smith, P. A. (2013). Building ethical leaders: A way to integrate and assess ethics education. *Journal of business ethics*, 115(1), 101-114.
- [6] Dzurani, A. C., Shortridge, R. T., & Smith, P. A. (2013). Building ethical leaders: A way to integrate and assess ethics education. *Journal of business ethics*, 115(1), 101-114.
- [7] Sims, R. R., & Felton, E. L. (2006). Designing and delivering business ethics teaching and learning. *Journal of business ethics*, 63(3), 297-312.
- [8] Boni, A., & Berjano, E. J. (2009). Ethical learning in higher education: The experience of the Technical University of Valencia. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 34(2), 205-213.
- [9] Wanxue, Q., & Hanwei*, T. (2004). The social and cultural background of contemporary moral education in China. *Journal of Moral Education*, 33(4), 465-480.